

Emotional Intelligence and Depression among College Students

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This study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and depression among college students. The inventories used for the study were Emotional Intelligence Scale (Goleman, 2007) and Beck Depression Inventory (Beck, Steer, & Brown, 1996). The statistical tools of correlation and t-test were used. The participants were randomly selected from numerous colleges from all over Kerala. The data collected have been scrutinised with the help of SPSS 20. The sampling was completed on the principles of simple random sampling. Results revealed that there is no relationship between emotional intelligence and depression. But two factors of emotional intelligence like Motivating oneself (MO) and empathy (EMP) are significantly correlated with Depression (BD). In addition, to that there is a significant difference in emotional intelligence on depression. High emotional intelligence decreases the effect of depression. Results also showed that sex is associated with depression and males show higher levels of depression than females.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, depression, college students

The prevalence of depression among college students has progressively increased in recent years, even exceptional that of the public, which has become a global phenomenon. Mounting research has focused on the topic, and the consensus is that the high prevalence of depression among college students cannot be ignored. The transformation from high school to university is filled with tension and requires significant adaptation. It is a critical period for the shift from late adolescence to adulthood or emerging adulthood, which is neither adolescence nor young adulthood but theoretically and analytically distinct from both periods. In the recent years the rate of depression among college students is increasing in an incredible amount. There are many risk factors for depression including life events, traumatic experiences etc. The influencing factors of college students' depression mainly fell into four categories: biological factors, personality and psychological state, college experience, and lifestyle (Ibrahim, Kelly, Adams, & Glazebrook, 2013).

The present study aims to understand the relationship between emotional intelligence and depression among college students. Emotional intelligence is the ability to know and interpret emotions and to recognize their significance and relation to problems, including their causes and solutions. Depression is rated by the World Health Organization as the 4th largest cause of global disease burden in terms of its impact on the individual sufferer, the family and society in general in terms of lost productivity. Emotional Intelligence (EI) is broadly defined as a set of abilities concerned with the regulation, management, control, and use of emotions in

decision-making, particularly in relation to the promotion of healthy and adaptive mental functioning (Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso, 2004). As such, EI intuitively offers a window into mental health, since the ability of individuals to understand their own emotional states or emotional problems is considered an important indicator of healthy mental functioning. The importance of feelings and emotions and their impact on people's lives is a new trend that has recently been at the forefront of people's lives as they try to deal with their environments (Salovey, 2001). As a result, new research has experienced a shift in focus from behaviors, ideas, and cognitive processes to emotions (Heesacker & Bradley, 1997). Consequently, emotional disorders have become the key element and the basis of psychological health (Kring & Bachorowski, 1999). The focus of modern theories is on emotions and self-regulation, and they also refer to the tensions and psychological stress which people go through in their daily lives. Emotions raise some issues and threats that may affect the people's health. These threats may affect people's physical, psychological, or social welfare (Edwards, 1998).

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence (EI) has been labelled many times in psychological theories. Serrat (2017) describes EI as "the ability, capacity, skill, or self-perceived ability to identify, assess, and manage the emotions of oneself of others, and of groups". Lyusin (2006) also mentioned that feelings and the derivative knowledge of emotions support mankind react better with others. EI is defined as the ability to know and understand emotions and to recognize their significance and relation to problems, including their causes and solutions (Mayer & Salovey, 1990). However, the best definition of EI is the accepted definition of Salovey and Meyer (1990) the process of dealing with emotions including the ability to have appropriate responses to show emotions and expression, both with the same person or with others. All this happens while trying to improve the level of life through the accomplishment of the capacity to adjust to those emotions. It is one of the forms of social intelligence, which includes the ability to distinguish and discriminate between your and others' feelings and utilize this

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knowledge in your intellectual, emotional, and physical behavior. Individuals differ in the level of skills that will help them to understand their feelings and the emotions of others, and then organize these sentiments and excitements and make use of them in raising the level of cooperative behavior. The organization of these skills and putting them into a practical framework is called "emotional intelligence" (Salovey & Mayer, 1990).

Though the field of emotional intelligence is a new one the word, emotional intelligence" itself was coined first and used in literary writing by Salovey and Mayer in 1990 (Cherniss, 2000) the concept has become immensely popular as it explains and provides evidence on how people with a good IQ sometimes fail and those who were school dropouts and considered stupid go on to become the most successful ones in their fields (Goleman, 1995). Some of the forerunners in the research on emotional intelligence Mayer, Salovey, Caruso, Goleman, Bar-On list out various characteristics which decide a person's emotional intelligence. While Mayer and Salovey (1990) take EI as a purely cognitive ability, Goleman and Bar-On view it as a personality trait. Mayer and Salovey's four branch model of EI lays emphasizes emotional perception, emotional assimilation, understanding and management (Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso, 2004), whereas Bar-On (2002) agrees on the qualities of emotional self-awareness, self-actualization, interpersonal relationship, reality testing, stress tolerance, optimism, happiness, etc. as those that decide the emotional intelligence of a person. Goleman (1998) on the other hand points out to emotional self-awareness, self- control, empathy, problem solving, conflict management, leadership, etc. as the characteristics of an emotionally intelligent person. The mixed ability model proposed by Bar-On emphasizes on how the personality traits influence a person's general well-being and Goleman's model focuses on workplace success (Stys & Brown, 2004).

The concept of EI emerged in the field of psychology at the end of 1930 when Thorndike wrote about social intelligence and defined it as "the ability to understand and manage social relations and the ability to behave wisely with others" (Gardner, 2000).

Depression

Depression is a psychological disorder marked by an obstinate lowering of mood and a condensed awareness in daily activities. It can affect the way a person thinks, behaves, feels, and functions in everyday life. As one of the most common mood disorders, it is stereotypically connected with enduring sadness, anxiety, loss of pleasure, and irritability. Individuals experiencing depression may report feelings such as sadness, anxiety, emptiness, hopelessness, helplessness, guilt, worthlessness, irritability, or restlessness. They may also lose interest in actions that once brought enjoyment. Difficulties with appetite-either reduced or increased-along with problems in concentration, memory, and decision-making are recurrently observed. Relationship issues may arise, and in severe cases, individuals may experience suicidal thoughts or engage in suicidal behavior (Beck & Alford, 2009).

Physical symptoms can also convey depression. These may comprise insomnia or excessive sleeping, persistent fatigue, body aches, digestive discomfort, and generally low energy. While depressed mood is a central symptom of major depressive disorder and other psychiatric conditions, it can also emerge as a temporary response to stressful life events such as loss or major change.

Furthermore, it may occur because of certain medical illnesses, medications, or treatment side effects. The DSM distinguishes between a depressive "episode," which refers to a temporary state of symptoms, and more enduring depressive tendencies, which may be long-standing features of a person's personality or emotional style (Katon & Ciechanowski, 2002).

Need and Significance

Formerly, psychologists have attempted to understand the strength of the relationship between various psychological functions and emotional intelligence (EI). They found that acquiring EI has a positive impact on success in life (Parker, Summerfields, Hogan, & Majeski, 2004; Vakola, Tsaousis, & Nikalaou, 2004).

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The purpose of this study is to examine the role of emotional intelligence in depression among college students. Understanding this relationship can help reduce the rate of depression by developing emotionally strong individuals. There has been a significant increase in interest regarding how we interact and how psychological experiences influence general health. It has become evident that positive emotions have an advantageous impact on strengthening the immune system, whereas negative emotions adversely affect psychological functioning (Herbert & Cohen, 1993).

The current study aims to explore how emotional intelligence (EI) is associated with levels of depression among students. This topic is significant because both EI and depression play an important role in shaping students' everyday experiences and academic adjustment in college. According to Svyantek and Rahim (2002), EI functions as a key interpersonal skill that enables individuals to manage relationships and social interactions effectively. Goleman (1998) suggested that EI may have a greater impact than cognitive intelligence, as it encompasses abilities that support achievement in academic, professional, and social domains. Based on previous research, it is expected that individuals with higher EI scores will demonstrate lower levels of depressive symptoms, as measured by Beck's Depression Inventory (Bulik, 2005).

Statement of the Problem

The problem to be focused on the study is entitled as "emotional intelligence and depression among college students."

Key Terms Defined

Emotional Intelligence: Emotional intelligence is 'the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships (Goleman, 1998).

Depression: Depression is a mood disorder that causes a persistent feeling of sadness and loss of interest and can interfere with our daily activities (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Review of Literature

Emotional Intelligence and Depression

Several empirical studies have examined the association between

emotional intelligence and depression across different age groups. Tannous and Matar (2010) investigated the relationship between depression and emotional intelligence among a sample of Jordanian children. The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between depression and emotional intelligence among children. Their study included 619 (365 females & 254 males) at sixth grade students from both public and private schools in Amman city. The findings indicated significant gender differences in stress management and overall emotional intelligence, with depressed female students demonstrating comparatively lower emotional intelligence than males. However, no gender differences were observed in the intrapersonal, interpersonal, or adaptability dimensions of emotional intelligence. The study employed correlational analysis to explore these relationships.

A growing body of research has consistently highlighted the role of emotional intelligence in maintaining mental health. Sutar and Patil (2018) reported a positive association between emotional intelligence and mental health among college students, suggesting that individuals with higher emotional intelligence are better equipped to cope with psychological challenges. Similarly, Velasco, Fernandez, Paez, and Campos (2006) demonstrated that emotional intelligence is significantly related to life adjustment among university students, indicating its importance in overall psychosocial functioning.

Further evidence was provided by Fernandez-Berrocal, Alcaide, Extremera, and Pizarro (2006) who examined emotional abilities among adolescents. Their findings revealed that effective mood regulation was positively associated with self-esteem, while higher levels of self-reported emotional intelligence were linked to lower levels of depression and anxiety. The study also emphasized that the ability to accurately identify and manage emotions contributes to better mental health outcomes.

In the Indian context, Ray, Sharma, and Tiwari (2020) explored the relationship between emotional intelligence and depression and confirmed a significant correlation between the two variables. The authors noted that rapid sociocultural changes, technological advancement, and increasing westernization have considerably influenced emotional functioning, well-being, and mental health. These transformations in social structure and lifestyle appear to affect individuals' emotional competencies and vulnerability to depressive symptoms.

Overall, the reviewed literature clearly indicates that emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in mental health and psychological adjustment. Higher emotional intelligence is consistently associated with lower levels of depression, emphasizing its importance in promoting emotional well-being across different populations.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out whether there exists any relationship between emotional intelligence and depression.
- To compare depression levels between individuals with high level of emotional intelligence and those with low of emotional intelligence
- To compare depression levels between male and female participants.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be a significant relationship between emotional

intelligence and depression.

- There will be a significant difference in depression levels between individuals with high and low levels of emotional intelligence.
- There will be a significant difference in depression levels between males and females

Method

Participants

This study was conducted in the educational sector consisting of various colleges in Kerala. The simple random sampling method was used and it consisted of 177 college students of aged between 18-23 including males and females.

Measures

Emotional Intelligence Scale (Goleman, 2007): Designed by Goleman and consists of 50 items. It assesses 4 different dimensions like self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, Empathy and Social skill

Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) (Beck, Steer, & Brown, 1996): The BDI is a popular scale used for the assessment of the intensity of depressive symptoms within both psychiatric and normal populations (Beck, Rush, Shaw, & Emery, 1979). The BDI consists of 21-items that assess the intensity of depressive symptomatology, such as negative mood, pessimism, guilt, sense of failure, suicidal thoughts, fatigue, and weight loss. For each item, respondents are asked to indicate which of four statements best describes the way they were feeling during the past week. The statements are scored according to the severity of symptomatology they reflect (0 = *symptom is absent*; 3 = *symptom is present & severe*). The BDI is a reliable and well-validated measure of depressive symptoms, discriminates subtypes of depression, and differentiates depression from anxiety. A total depression score is obtained by summing the rating of the 21 items, yielding scores that range from 0-63.

Procedure

The questionnaire will be a self-administering one. Instructions are printed at the beginning of the inventories. Response space, () will be provided against each item and the respondent will be required to mark the appropriate column representing his / her response.

Participants are approached individually during the working hours in their respective organizations with the help of the concerned administration. The participants are informed about the purpose of the study and confidentiality will be assured. Sufficient time will be given to respond to the questionnaires and then the data collections will be made. Scoring will be done as per the manuals.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected for the present investigation were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques to address the objectives of the study. Computer-based analysis was carried out using SPSS (Version 20) to test the stated hypotheses. The statistical methods employed for data analysis included correlation analysis and the t-test.

Results and Discussion

Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Depression

To examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and

depression, the Karl Pearson productmoment correlation technique was applied. The obtained correlation coefficients for the variables under study are shown in Table 1. The analysis was performed using the full set of data, comprising seven variables, namely the five components of emotional intelligence, the total emotional intelligence score, and the overall depression score.

Table 1

Correlation Matrix of Emotional Intelligence and Depression (Correlation Analysis among the 7 Variables of the Study)

	SA	ME	MO	EMP	SS	BD	EMT
SA							
ME	.274**						
MO	.228**	.553**					
EMP	.452**	.329*	.307**				
SS	.549**	.455**	.404**	.446**			
BD	.106	-.070	-.168 *	.173*	.059		
EMT	.736**	.679**	.660**	.733**	.784**	.045	

Note **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In the total correlations 17 are significant. Out of them 15 are significant at 0.01 levels and 2 of them are significant at 0.05 level.

Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Depression

There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and depression. But two factors of emotional intelligence like Motivating oneself (MO) ($r = -0.168, p < .05$) and empathy (EMP) ($r = 0.173, p < .05$) are significantly correlated with Depression (BD). The results show a significant negative relationship between self-motivation (MO) and depression, indicating that as levels of self-motivation increase, depressive symptoms tend to decrease. This inverse association suggests that individuals who possess stronger internal drive are less likely to experience higher levels of depression.

A decline in motivation is widely recognized as a central characteristic of depression, though it can also stem from other psychological or environmental influences. Depression frequently drains emotional vitality and reduces persistence, making it difficult for individuals to engage in purposeful, goal-directed activities.

Self-motivation refers to an individual's capacity to use inner drive and emotional energy to pursue and accomplish goals. It encourages proactive behavior, sustained commitment, and determination even when facing difficulties or failure. By fostering persistence and psychological resilience, self-motivation helps individuals remain involved in purposeful activities. This quality can act as a buffer against the development of depressive symptoms (Beck, Steer, & Brown, 1996).

The findings further reveal a significant positive association between empathy and depression. This suggests that higher levels of empathy are related to increased levels of depressive symptoms. Empathy refers to the ability to perceive, share, and comprehend the emotional experiences of others.

Depression is a widespread mental health condition that leads to

distress, reduced functioning, and, in severe cases, a decline in overall quality and expectancy of life. Research indicates that individuals with major depressive disorder may experience disturbances in emotional empathy, and such difficulties can intensify depressive symptoms (Cusi et al., 2011). Thus, alterations in empathetic processing may play a role in the severity and progression of depression.

Self-awareness (SA) is significantly inter correlated with motivational emotion (ME) ($r = 0.274, p < .05$), empathy ($r = 0.452, p < .01$), social skill ($r = 0.549, p < .01$), and emotional intelligence (EMT) ($r = 0.736, p < .01$). Motivating emotions (ME) significantly inter correlated with motivating oneself ($r = 0.533, p < .05$) and empathy ($r = 0.329, p < .05$). Social skill correlated with EMT ($r = 0.784, p < .05$). Motivating oneself (MO) significantly inter correlated with empathy (EMP) ($r = 0.307, p < .01$), social skill ($r = 0.404, p < .05$), EMT ($r = 0.660, p < .05$). Empathy significantly inter-correlated with social skill ($r = 0.446, p < .01$), EMT ($r = 0.733, p < .01$). EMT is also significantly correlated with EMP ($r = 0.733, p < .01$).

The result also shows that Emotional intelligence and all its variables are interrelated. EI is not just about emotions; it is a combination of emotions, feelings, thoughts, and behaviors (Vander Voort, 2006).

Emotional intelligence consists of five core components: self-awareness, self-control, intrinsic motivation, empathy, and social skills. It refers to the capacity to recognize, understand, and regulate one's own emotions effectively, while also responding appropriately to the emotions of others. This ability helps individuals manage stress, resolve interpersonal conflicts, cope with challenges, and build healthy relationships.

Large-scale assessments of emotional intelligence among men and women suggest certain general patterns. Women, on average, tend to show greater emotional awareness and empathy, along with higher levels of optimism, adaptability, and self-confidence. Men, in contrast, are often found to manage stress more effectively. Despite these trends, the overall similarities between genders are much greater than the differences. Many men demonstrate high interpersonal sensitivity, and many women exhibit strong emotional resilience under pressure. Research findings by King (1999), Sutarso (1999), Wing and Love (2001), and Singh (2002) indicate that females generally score higher on measures of emotional intelligence compared to males.

Role of Emotional Intelligence on Depression

To assess the effect of emotional intelligence on depression among college students, an independent samples t-test was conducted. The second hypothesis stated that emotional intelligence would significantly differ based on the level of depression. Table 2 displays the mean emotional intelligence scores for the respective depression groups.

The analysis yielded a t-value of 2.077, which reached statistical significance at the 0.05 level. This outcome indicates a meaningful difference in emotional intelligence between groups with varying levels of depression. Therefore, emotional intelligence, treated as the independent variable, appears to have a significant impact on depression, the dependent variable.

Table 2
t-test Score of Emotional Intelligence on Depression

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal Variances Assumed	.158	.691	-2.077*	175	.039	-5.573	2.683	-10.868	-.278
Depression Equal Variances not Assumed			-2.372*	13.272	.033	-5.573	2.349	-10.637	-.508

A negative t-value indicates that the mean difference between the groups is in the opposite direction, and when the p-value is below .05, this difference is statistically significant. This pattern reflects an inverse association between the variables. In practical terms, individuals with higher emotional intelligence tend to report lower levels of depression. Therefore, the findings demonstrate that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on depression, leading to the acceptance of the second hypothesis. Evidence indicates that people with depression often struggle to accurately identify and understand their own feelings as well as the emotions of others, pointing to an inverse relationship between depression and emotional intelligence. However, findings are not always uniform across contexts. For example, Tannous and Matar (2010) in their study on Jordanian children, observed that among those with depressive symptoms, boys obtained higher emotional intelligence scores compared to girls. This highlights that gender differences in emotional intelligence within depressed groups may vary depending on cultural and situational factors.

The roots of emotional intelligence can be traced to classical Indian philosophy, particularly in texts such as the Bhagavad Gita, the Upanishads, and the Vedas. Concepts like Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam, which promotes the idea of the world as a single family beyond divisions and prejudice, and Atma Bodha, which stresses self-realization and harmony with the larger universe over material gain, reflect early understandings of emotional awareness and collective responsibility (Gopraj & Sharma, 2011). From an Indian cultural viewpoint, emotional intelligence also integrates moral and social values, including reverence for elders, compassion toward others, commitment to one's duties (dharma), and the practice of kindness and ahimsa (non-violence). These teachings guide for regulating emotions, expressing them appropriately, and navigating social and cultural situations with sensitivity and balance (Anand, 2017).

Table 4
t-test Score of Sex on Emotional Intelligence

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal Variances Assumed	4.539	.035	.308	175	.758	.995	3.226	-5.371	7.361
EMT Equal Variances not Assumed			.335	168.716	.738	.995	2.973	-4.873	6.863

Table 3
Comparison of the Mean and SD of Emotional Intelligence on Depression
Group Statistics

	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Depression	1(Low)	12	9.50	7.764	2.241
	2(High)	165	15.07	9.048	.704

According to the mean values reported in Table 3, the group classified as having high emotional intelligence obtained a mean depression score of 15.07 when compared with the low emotional intelligence group. This pattern indicates differences in depressive symptoms across levels of emotional intelligence. Overall, the trend suggests that greater emotional intelligence is associated with reduced depressive symptoms.

In general, it is anticipated that individuals who score higher on emotional intelligence assessments will obtain lower scores on the Beck Depression Inventory, reflecting fewer symptoms of depression (Bulik, 2005).

Influence of Socio-demographic Variables (Age, Sex, & Education) on Emotional Intelligence and Depression

Sex and Emotional Intelligence

To examine the role of emotional intelligence and socio demographic variables (age, sex, & education) in predicting depression among college students, an independent sample t-test was conducted. The findings indicate that these variables do not have a significant influence on emotional intelligence except for sex. Table 4 presents the t-test scores for sex, which is considered the primary socio-demographic factor, in relation to emotional intelligence.

The data presented in Table 4 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in emotional intelligence between male and female students. This suggests that emotional intelligence levels are largely similar across genders.

Comparable findings were reported by Sutar and Patil (2018) in their study on emotional intelligence and mental health among MPSC aspirants, where no meaningful gender differences were observed. Taken together, these results imply that emotional intelligence does not vary substantially between males and females.

At the same time, earlier investigations have produced inconsistent findings. Certain studies suggest that males with depressive symptoms may report marginally higher emotional intelligence than females. In contrast, Sánchez et al. (2008) found that women typically obtain higher scores on measures of emotional intelligence.

Such variations may be linked to commonly observed behavioural patterns, as females are often described as more emotionally expressive, empathetic, and attentive to social cues/qualities closely connected to emotional intelligence. Differences in upbringing,

gender roles, and cultural norms may further shape these outcomes.

While numerous studies point to higher emotional intelligence scores among females, other research (Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2002; Fernández-Berrocal et al., 2005; Austin et al., 2005; Bindu & Thomas, 2006) suggests that gender differences are becoming less pronounced over time, particularly with shifts in cultural expectations and increased educational opportunities.

These investigations further note that males may show relative strengths in areas such as managing emotions effectively, controlling impulses, coping with stress, and applying problem-solving strategies. Such findings indicate that gender-based patterns in emotional intelligence are complex and may be influenced by social and environmental factors.

Sex and Depression

To determine whether socio-demographic variables (age, sex, & education) influence depression among college students, a t-test analysis was carried out.

Table 5

t-test Score of Sex on Depression

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Depression	Equal Variances Assumed	16.344	.000	4.666***	175	.000	6.213	1.331	3.585	8.840
	Equal Variances not Assumed			4.355***	109.555	.000	6.213	1.426	3.386	9.040

The data presented in Table 5 indicate a statistically significant difference in depression scores between males and females. The independent samples t-test produced a t-value of 4.666, which was significant at the 0.001 level. This confirms that depression varies by sex, leading to partial acceptance of the third hypothesis.

Furthermore, the analysis shows that the remaining socio-demographic factors examined in the study did not demonstrate a significant effect on depression.

In the study "Emotional Intelligence and Depression: The Moderator Role of Gender" (Fernández-Berrocal, 2012) it was found that men with lower emotional intelligence were at greater risk of experiencing depressive symptoms, whereas the relationship followed a different pattern among women. This suggests that gender may influence how emotional intelligence relates to depression.

Table 6

Comparison of Mean and SD of Sex and Depression Group Statistics

	Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Depression	1(Male)	66	18.59	10.002	1.231
	2(Female)	111	12.38	7.591	.720

Table 6 compares the average depression scores of male and female students. The mean values indicate that males obtained a

higher depression score ($M = 18.59$) than females.

The third hypothesis stated that depression would significantly differ based on sex. The statistical findings confirm this assumption, demonstrating that sex plays a role in depression levels, with male students reporting greater depressive symptoms than female students.

In addition, people who possess clear insight into their emotions and are skilled at managing or restoring their emotional balance generally exhibit higher levels of self-esteem, an important marker of psychological health. The capacity for emotional repair is also associated with improved regulation of intrusive and repetitive thoughts that commonly occur during periods of stress (Salovey et al., 1995).

Tenability of Hypotheses

The study proposed three primary hypotheses. Considering the findings, the validity of each hypothesis is evaluated and discussed below:

First Hypothesis

There will be significant relationships between emotional intelligence and depression.

The findings reveal that total emotional intelligence does not have a statistically significant relationship with depression. However,

Accordingly, the first hypothesis receives partial support, as only certain dimensions of emotional intelligence, rather than the overall score, are significantly related to depression.

Second Hypothesis

There will be a significant difference of emotional intelligence and depression.

A t-test was conducted to examine the influence of emotional intelligence on depression. The findings reveal a significant relationship, indicating that higher emotional intelligence is associated with lower levels of depression. Thus, the second hypothesis is confirmed.

Third Hypothesis

There will be a significant difference of socio-demographic variables (age, sex, & education) on emotional intelligence and depression.

An independent samples t-test was performed to determine whether socio-demographic factors influence emotional intelligence and depression. The analysis indicates that sex is significantly associated with both emotional intelligence and depression scores. In contrast, variables such as age and educational level do not demonstrate a statistically meaningful impact on either construct.

Based on these outcomes, the third hypothesis is considered partially supported.

Major Findings of the Study

The major findings of the present research are as follows:

- There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and depression.
- Two components of emotional intelligence-Motivating Oneself (MO) and Empathy (EMP)-show a significant correlation with depression (BD).
- There is a significant interrelationship among emotional intelligence and its sub-dimensions.
- There is a significant difference of emotional intelligence on depression.
- Higher levels of emotional intelligence reduce the severity of depression.
- There is a significant difference in sex and depression, with males showing higher levels of depression compared to females.:

Implications of the Study

The current investigation aimed to explore the association between emotional intelligence and depression. The findings add to the growing body of literature in this field. Overall, emotional intelligence was not found to have a statistically significant relationship with depression. Nevertheless, two specific dimensions-Motivating Oneself (MO) and Empathy (EMP)-were significantly related to depression (BD).

Furthermore, the analysis demonstrated that emotional intelligence exerts a significant effect on depression, indicating that higher emotional intelligence may be linked to lower levels of depressive symptoms.

The findings further demonstrated a significant influence of sex on depression, with male participants reporting higher levels of depressive symptoms than females. This outcome suggests the importance of examining gender-related factors in future research to

better understand variations in depression. The results also underscore the need for continued investigation into the link between emotional intelligence and depression. In addition, they point to the value of developing pilot interventions-such as individual and group counselling programs-to support college students who are experiencing depressive symptoms and to strengthen their emotional competencies.

Limitations of the Present Study and Suggestions for Future Research

The study is subject to certain limitations that should be acknowledged. Future investigations could include additional variables that may affect emotional intelligence and depression to obtain a more comprehensive perspective. As the sample was confined to Kerala, comparative studies involving participants from other states would help identify possible regional variations and enhance generalizability.

Moreover, adopting a mixed-method design that integrates quantitative measures with qualitative approaches may provide deeper insight into the complexities of emotional intelligence and depression. It is anticipated that subsequent researchers will build upon these suggestions and further examine this dynamic and important area of study.

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